

Fire Detection for Emergency Responders using X

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Abstract—Increased traffic on social media platforms, such as X (formerly known as Twitter), is associated with disaster events and consequently, fire incidents. Although detecting fires through social media has garnered research interest in recent years, managing the overwhelming volume of daily posts remains challenging. Efficient collection and filtering of fire-related posts are crucial for detecting fires through X. The FireXPosts dataset presented in this article is a collection of posts from Canada and Greece, binarily annotated to aid emergency responders effectively. We train and evaluate uni-modal and bi-modal models for filtering fire-relevant posts and establishing performance baselines on the FireXPosts dataset. Experimental results indicate relatively similar performance between the text modality and the best-performing bi-modal models, suggesting that visual supervision does not positively influence the outcomes of late fusion models.

Keywords—Bi-Modal Fusion, Fire Detection, Relevance Estimation, Concept Extraction, Twitter/X Data

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, the relationship between social media activity on platforms like X (formerly known as Twitter) and the geographical occurrence of wildfires has garnered attention among researchers [1]. Detecting crises such as wildfires through social media, has been an ongoing area of research, particularly with the rise in popularity of such platforms [2]. However, as the volume of daily posts continues to grow, the importance of efficiently collecting and filtering these posts becomes increasingly critical.

To manage that, some methods prioritize location extraction [3], [4] to compensate for the lack of geolocation data in crowdsourced information. Others emphasize text relevance estimation [5], [6] to automatically identify and remove irrelevant data, providing only pertinent information to end-users. Furthermore, there are crisis-related approaches that extract higher-level concepts [7]–[10], while others focus on specific visual characteristics in images [11]–[13].

A recent review article [5], emphasized the need to clearly define relevance, relation, and informativeness when annotating crisis-related social media posts. The authors extensively discuss these definitions for various public crisis datasets, including the Disaster Corpus 2020 (DC2020) [14] and CrisisMMD [15].

In the current study, preliminary experiments done on the three wildfire-related subsets of DC2020 were assessed using the FireXPosts dataset, where they exhibited a high incidence of false positive predictions. This outcome was expected since the DC2020 labels as '1' posts related to wildfires but in a broader sense. Consequently, it does not align with the annotation guidelines applied for the FireXPosts labeling. This suggests the presence of application-specific challenges that remain underexplored in the existing literature. Additionally, the lack of publicly available datasets in languages other than English presents a significant obstacle, given the necessity to deploy filtering and detection frameworks in other linguistic contexts [16]. Contributions of this article can be summarized as follow:

- Creation of the FireXPosts dataset, binarily annotated for emergency response relevant posts from Canada and Greece, including a Greek language subset.
- Proposal and assessment of a bi-modal framework with three initially independent modules for collection and filtering of Twitter/X posts.
- Design of a shallow neural tail for late multi-modal fusion, intended to compare predictability against uni-modal models and especially text relevance estimation.

We plan to release the FireXPosts dataset once further research is finalized. In addition, we will share the five cross-validation folds used for training and evaluation, to ensure the reproducibility and falsifiability of the presented results.

The rest of the article is structured as follows: Section II provides an overview of state-of-the-art research on detecting

crisis and wildfire events in social media data. Section III outlines the proposed crawler and the filtering framework. Section IV presents and analyzes the experimental findings for visual, textual, and fused analyses, followed by conclusions in Section V.

II. RELATED WORK

Researchers have explored detection of crisis and wildfire events on social media, using various textual (Section II-A) or visual (Section II-B) representations. However, studies that focus on using multimodal filtering for collecting social media data (Section II-C) are limited.

A. Textual Analysis

In the textual module, the current work explores two primary categories of analysis: methods based on *location extraction* and those focused on *relevance text estimation*.

Location Extraction aims to address the absence of geolocation information in crowdsourced data, with the primary goal of extracting location entities from text posts like tweets. This process has evolved from rule-based algorithms to machine learning, like using Long short-term memory (LSTM) [4] neural networks. A significant advancement in Natural Language Processing (NLP) occurred with the introduction of Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) [3], ushering in a new era in the field. These models address the challenge of long-term dependency by retaining information across multiple sentences.

Relevance Estimation is employed to automatically identify irrelevant posts, allowing for their removal, and the provision of only pertinent data to end users. Modern systems utilize NLP techniques, such as supervised Machine Learning ML models like Support Vector Machines (SVM) or Decision Trees (DT), for binary classification to assess relevance in crisis contexts [17]. However, there's a gap in NLP applications for textual wildfire detection despite research focusing on other disasters like earthquakes and floods [18].

B. Visual Analysis

Visual analysis is categorized into two primary methods: *concept based* and *image-based* approaches.

Concept-based Detection approaches extract higher-level fire related concepts (e.g., contextual information) that enhance the understanding and characterization of images. Such methods, usually employ Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DCNNs) [7], [8]. DCNNs typically comprise multiple layers of feature extractors and can serve as both standalone classifiers and generators of image features. Some methods used an extra layer before the classification layers in the GoogLeNet architecture [9], while others are based on SqueezeNet, a variant of GoogLeNet [10], which fine-tunes a CNN model for fire detection.

Image-based Fire Detection techniques focus on specific visual characteristics present in images to detect fires. Historically, such methods relied on handcrafted feature extraction techniques, such as color and texture analysis, alongside traditional classifiers like Naive Bayes (NB) and K-Nearest Neighbors

(KNN) [11]. More recently, Graph Neural Network (GNN) models have been explored for fire detection based on feature similarity from multi-view images [12]. In a method outlined in [13], flame regions were identified by subtracting flame and background colors. Features such as area and color, combined with logistic regression, determined the fire probability in the region of interest. However, the traditional ML techniques relied heavily on feature engineering, which proved to be crude, time demanding and ineffective in many cases [19]. Consequently, deep learning models pre-trained on ImageNet [20], including AlexNet [10], GoogLeNet [21], VGG16 [22], ResNet50 [22], MobileNet [23] and DenseNet [24], have significantly improved fire detection accuracy and robustness.

C. Textual and Visual Late Fusion Analysis

Multi-modal fusion and integration of both textual and visual information, has been pivotal in disaster-related social media applications, addressing the heterogeneous nature of data on these platforms. The CrisisMMD dataset [15] catalyzed the integration of textual and visual modalities for predicting informativeness, damage severity and others. In [25], the authors utilized text, image, and geolocation data from Twitter posts to enhance situational awareness, specifically during flood events. Furthermore, [26] described the development of a mid-late multi-modal network applied to various tasks within the CrisisMMD dataset. Despite ongoing research into multi-modal processing [27], there is a noticeable gap in fire incident applications using textual and visual data from platforms like X. Fusion techniques at late stages of a multi-modal framework, known as late fusion methods, are common in many disaster contexts [27]. This approach aligns with practical considerations, as multi-modal frameworks, especially those encompassing multiple modules, are typically developed independently.

III. FRAMEWORK

The crawler's architecture, depicted in Figure 1, consists of three main components: (a) the Crawling Module (Section III-A), responsible for connecting to X's API to monitor, detect, and gather posts, (b) the Analysis Module Block, which processes the collected posts, and (c) the Late Fusion Block, merges outcomes from textual and visual analysis (in the grey box). The Analysis Module Block includes tasks such as Location Extraction and Relevance Estimation from post's text (Section III-B), as well as Image Concepts Extraction and Fire Detection (Section III-C). Further details on each component are provided in the subsequent sections.

A. Crawler Module

The crawler module is a vital component of the data collection process, comprising several key elements such as activity monitoring, data retrieval, parsing, and storage. It connects to X's API to extract near-real-time social media posts concerning wildfires. Periodic queries to X's Recent Tweet Counts¹ through the Recent Search² endpoint enable event detection and retrieval

¹<https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/twitter-api/tweets/counts/introduction>

²<https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/twitter-api/tweets/search/introduction>

Fig. 1. Crawler architecture

of relevant posts. By monitoring X’s public stream and applying filters for specific keywords or users, the crawler efficiently handles large data volumes while adhering to ethical standards and X’s terms of service for lawful data acquisition. Its modular and scalable architecture facilitates easy integration of new features and updates, ensuring effective monitoring and analysis of wildfire-related posts.

To oversee post activity, the crawler utilizes an outlier detection approach employing an isolation forest algorithm. The methodology involves training a model to identify outliers based on historical post counts and triggering the retrieval posts during notable increases. Furthermore, the crawler formulates queries with rules³ every 30 minutes to fetch posts the past 7 days from Recent Search endpoint, filtered by keywords, phrases, and user accounts related to wildfires. These retrieved posts undergo comprehensive analysis through parallel HTTP requests to analysis web services. Subsequently, enriched posts are stored in a MongoDB database for further processing and analysis.

B. Textual Analysis

Location Extraction from post text aims to detect location references within social media text. Despite the frequent absence of geolocation details in post metadata, the necessity of locating events, like wildfires on a map remains essential. To address this challenge, a Location Extraction module has been developed to detect locations from posts and associate them with precise coordinates in the World Geodetic System (WGS 84) [28]. It follows a three-step process: (a) Text Processing, where text extracted from posts is inputted in an LSTM network; (b) Location Detection, which identifies location-indicating words or phrases and assigns a Named Entity Recognition label; and (c) API Query, querying the OpenStreetMap API to retrieve geolocation data using the assigned labels for exact coordinates.

³<https://developer.twitter.com/en/docs/twitter-api/tweets/search/integrate/build-a-query>

The module outputs an array containing the place’s complete name, precise coordinates, and coordinate reference system.

Relevance Estimation aims to assess the relevance of social media text to fire events. Development of this module is based on supervised binary ML classifiers. Models evaluated include several traditional binary classifiers such as Support Vector Machines and Logistic Regression (LR) while the novel Born Rule Classifier (BR) [29] was employed as a faster and modern statistical method. The output of Relevance Estimation models is a probability distribution, indicating the likelihood of the text belonging to class fire-irrelevant (i.e. ‘0’) or fire-relevant (i.e. ‘1’).

C. Visual Analysis

Concept-based Detection involves categorizing input data into classes using a multi-classifier. This method relies on a framework utilizing Caffe [30] and employs a 22-layer GoogleNet network initially trained on a subset of 5055 ImageNet concepts. Adjustments combine similar concepts and eliminate specialized and rare ones, reducing the classification layer from 5055 dimensions to 345, to target TRECVID Semantic concepts [31]. The process entails feeding an image into the concept extraction module, which utilizes a fine-tuned Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) for evaluation. This evaluation produces a list of concepts with their probabilities. The visual concept extraction module swiftly analyzes images in posts, offering valuable insights into their relevance to topics like fire incidents and retrieving similar content across platforms. Operating independently as a web service, it only requires a social media image URL as input, generating a JSON string with the concept scores chosen for the fire related application. In the current article 10 concepts were chosen for classifying content from the FireXPosts dataset: Explosion_fire, Truck, Fire_Truck, Outdoor, Fields, Forest, Helicopter_Hovering, Landscape, Trees, Vegetation.

Image-based Fire Detection encompasses creating and refining a machine learning model capable of identifying fire in input images, while minimizing false positives to prevent erroneous alerts. Additionally, prioritizing inference latency is essential to cater to end users in near real-time. To this end, state-of-the-art lightweight Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), some specialized for fire detection tasks, were selected. Regardless of their prior training, all models underwent transfer learning, initialized with baseline weights and trained on a custom image dataset (Section IV-D) to adapt them to the task of identifying fire in posts' images. Following training and evaluation on a separate set of images, the models output a JSON Object Array with the fire probability for each post image, considering an image to depict fire if the probability exceeds 0.5.

D. Textual and Visual Late Fusion Analysis

A simple late fusion approach combines predictions from independently trained uni-modal models. A more advanced strategy involves late fusion in which modalities are combined while training the whole model on a multi-modal dataset. Focusing on easily reusable and independently developed uni-modal services, we explore three fusion methodologies of the first kind. Specifically, we merge the analysis from Relevance Estimation, Concepts-based Extraction, and Image-based Fire Detection. The tri-module framework includes 10 scores predicted from the concept extraction module, a single prediction score from the image fire detection module, and a single prediction score from the text relevance estimation model.

1) *Concatenation Classifier*: The concatenation classifier approach, creates a vector representation per post by concatenating 12 probability scores: 10 from the Concept-based Extraction module, 1 from the Image-based fire detection module, and 1 from the text Relevance Estimation module. These vectors train a ML classifier, assessed with 5-fold cross-validation on the FireXPosts dataset.

2) *Majority Voting*: In the Majority Voting approach, binary predictions ('0' or '1') are independently selected from the three uni-modal systems. A post is considered relevant if at least two out of the three modalities identify it as such. While predicting binary labels from single scoring modules is straightforward, for concept extraction scores, we again train traditional classifiers using FireXPosts' concepts extraction scores to employ their predictions for the Majority Voting technique.

3) *Shallow Neural Tail*: In our filtering framework, three modules are utilized, with two of them being based on visual models. To leverage this structure strategically, a shallow neural network tail classifier has been designed. This classifier incorporates three combination nodes: N1, which takes in the 10 concepts extraction scores from each post, N2, utilizing the output from N1 along with the image fire detection score of the post to form the visual component, and N3, which integrates the outputs from N2 and the text relevance estimation score of the post. N3's output is then inputted in a sigmoid classifier to produce a final relevance estimation score.

TABLE I
DATASET STATISTICS

Language	Tweets	Images	Relevant Tweets	Irrelevant Tweets
English	1400	1830	613	787
Greek	582	609	204	378

IV. EXPERIMENTS

The following section covers dataset descriptions, experimental setup, and detailed results. In the case of textual analysis, classifiers were trained using three traditional text representation methods: Bag of Words (BoW), Term Frequency (TF), and Term Frequency - Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF). In all cases trained on FireXPosts (i.e. Tables II, III, VI), the evaluated classifiers include: Linear Support Vector Machine (LinearSVM), Polynomial Support Vector Machine (PolySVM), Logistic Regression (LR), Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF) and the Born Rule Classifier (BR). Tables II, III, VI present the four best-performing classifiers per language. In Table IV the Image-based Fire Detection model is evaluated on the Fire-related Image dataset. Best performing classifiers of each case are finally gathered into Table V, in which the Image-based Fire Detection module is also assessed on images from FireXPosts, accordingly.

A. Dataset

Two datasets were used in this article, the Fire-related Image dataset and the new FireXPosts dataset. The Fire-related Image dataset was utilized for training of Image-based Fire detection model, which was evaluated on the FireXPosts as an uni-modal case. Other datasets have been used for prior experimentation like the DC2020 [14] for textual analysis, but as mentioned it was dropped for this application due to high rates of false positives on FireXPosts.

- **Fire-related Image dataset.** In the absence of benchmark datasets for image fire detection, a custom dataset was created, with 20.7K images for training and 1K for testing. This dataset includes images of fire, as well as similar-looking objects (e.g., lanterns) to improve robustness and reduce false alarms, along with non-fire scenarios. Images were sourced from various channels, including X, online platforms, and photos taken during SILVANUS⁴ pilot exercises.
- **FireXPosts dataset.** It includes posts with textual and visual information binarily annotated, collected from Canada and Greece, with a subset of Greek posts. It consists of 1982 tweets, curated to target fire-relevant content for emergency response purposes. Human annotation involved three annotators, determining the final relevance label by majority voting. Table I provides statistics for both languages, including total tweets per language, associated images and relevance to fires. In each post, only the first image was retained for evaluation. The annotators adhered to the following guidelines: label '1' denoted

⁴<https://silvanus-project.eu/>

real-time events regarding fire incidents, while '0' covered metaphorical uses of fire-related terms, fire hazard alerts, temporally misplaced fire-related news streams, and political commentary without immediate relevance for responders.

TABLE II
EXPERIMENTS I-A: TEXT MODELS RESULTS ON FIREXPOSTS

Language	Model	Acc	Prec	Rec	F1
English	TF-IDF & LinearSVM	0.78	0.73	0.76	0.74
	TF & LR	0.75	0.70	0.73	0.71
	TF-IDF & DT	0.68	0.74	0.62	0.67
	BoW&BR	0.77	0.76	0.73	0.75
Greek	TF-IDF & LinearSVM	0.90	0.85	0.86	0.86
	TF-IDF & BR	0.89	0.85	0.84	0.84
	BoW & LR	0.87	0.77	0.86	0.81
	TF-IDF & RF	0.86	0.72	0.85	0.78

B. Experimental Settings

The framework’s Crawler was developed using Python and the Tweepy library. Training and evaluation durations for all classifiers in Tables III, III and VI, were under 5 minutes due to the dataset’s small size. That’s not the case though for the shallow neural tail, where the training time was about 10 minutes on an Intel® Core™ i7-3770K CPU. FireXPosts was split into 5-folds for cross-validation to mitigate statistical biases. For the Image-based Fire Detection module, the chosen model required 12 hours for training on a NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1660 Ti GPU. Table IV summarizes the models investigated for the binary fire detection task. The models selected for the experiments include Xception, MobileNet, ShuffleNetV2-OnFire, and NasNet-A-OnFire. Xception is a large model with a size of 250 MB, 22 million parameters, and 17.0 GFLOPs. MobileNet has a size of 25 MB, 4 million parameters, and 1.2 GFLOPs. NasNet-A-OnFire has a size of 10 MB, 3 million parameters, and 0.7 GFLOPs, while ShuffleNetV2-OnFire is the smallest with a size of 2 MB, 0.2 million parameters, and 0.06 GFLOPs.

Finally, all models were evaluated on FireXPosts using four common binary classification metrics: Accuracy (Acc), Precision (Prec), Recall (Rec), and F1-score (F1). The primary metric for preferring one model over another is the F1-score; however, if the values are close, we then consider Accuracy for a more robust choice. Classifiers trained on FireXPosts were assessed using both training and testing set metrics to more effectively monitor model’s behavior. Whenever the gap between training and testing accuracies exceeded 0.1, several regularization techniques were considered. Regularization parameters are exclusively mentioned for the best performing classifier per case. In instances where metrics exhibit equal or larger values, we bolded both, to improve clarity in presentation.

C. Experiment I: Textual Analysis

TableII presents the average metric scores derived from the five-cross-validation folds on the FireXPosts dataset. The results on the top part of table present the results for English language, while the reaming part of the table has the results for the Greek language. For each language, the four best performing

TABLE III
EXPERIMENTII-A: CONCEPT EXTRACTIONS CLASSIFIERS RESULTS ON FIREXPOSTS

Language	Model	Acc	Prec	Rec	F1
English	LinearSVM	0.65	0.48	0.63	0.54
	LR	0.63	0.40	0.62	0.48
	DT	0.65	0.63	0.59	0.61
	RF	0.69	0.66	0.64	0.65
Greek	PolySVM	0.65	0.07	0.62	0.13
	BR	0.66	0.38	0.56	0.44
	DT	0.64	0.23	0.53	0.30
	RF	0.66	0.23	0.56	0.32

TABLE IV
EXPERIMENT II-B: COMPARISON OF FIRE DETECTION MODELS ON FIRE-RELATED IMAGE DATASET.

Model	Acc	Prec	Rec	F1
Xception [32]	0.93	0.88	0.96	0.92
MobileNet [33]	0.89	0.82	0.93	0.87
NasNet-A-OnFire [34]	0.88	0.86	0.85	0.85
ShuffleNetV2-OnFire [34]	0.94	0.93	0.91	0.92

models (combinations of representation and classifying method) are presented. We highlight with bold formatting the best performing models for each language based on the f1-score metric. The highest-performing model for Greek, i.e. TF-IDF & LinearSVM achieved optimal results with the regularization parameter C set to 0.6. For the English language, the BoW & BR model yielded the highest F1-score value. Regarding the Greek language, TF-IDF & LinearSVM generally achieves the highest values, with only two ties with BoW & LR on precision and recall.

D. Experiment II: Visual Analysis

In the concept-based detection experiments (Table III), again the four best-performing classifiers are presented. In the case of the English language images, the RF model achieves the highest values for all metrics, with a significant difference in precision. Additionally, in the experiments conducted on the Greek language, the BR model exhibits the highest values in most metrics, achieving the same accuracy as the RF classifier.

Regarding Image-based fire-detection, the models chosen for the conducted experiments include Xception [32], MobileNet [33], ShuffleNetV2-OnFire, [34] and NasNet-A-OnFire [34]. The latter two have been previously trained in fire detection tasks. As described in Section III-C, transfer learning was employed as the technique, wherein the first two models utilized baseline weights pre-trained on ImageNet, while the weights provided by the authors were used for the last two models.

During training, adjustments were made to both the convolutional layers and the final fully connected layers of the networks using the training dataset to optimize their performance. In addition to evaluating the models’ performance in fire detection using the F1-score, consideration was given to another factor: the models’ size and computational complexity, measured in GigaFLOPs (floating-point operations in billions), which directly impacts inference latency.

TABLE V
EXPERIMENT III-A: UNI-MODAL AND MULTI-MODAL RESULTS EVALUATED ON FIREXPOSTS DATASET

Language	Methods&Modules	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-Score
English	Relevance Estimation Module II	0.77	0.76	0.73	0.75
	Image-based Fire Detection Module	0.64	0.68	0.37	0.47
	Concepts Extraction Module III	0.69	0.66	0.64	0.65
	Concatenation Classifier VI	0.78	0.72	0.77	0.74
	Majority Voting	0.72	0.73	0.59	0.65
	Shallow Neural Tail Classifier	0.78	0.75	0.75	0.75
Greek	Relevance Estimation Module II	0.90	0.85	0.86	0.86
	Image Based Fire Detection Module	0.62	0.44	0.28	0.34
	Concepts Extraction Module III	0.66	0.38	0.56	0.44
	Concatenation Classifier VI	0.81	0.90	0.8	0.85
	Majority Voting	0.46	0.60	0.25	0.35
	Shallow Neural Tail Classifier	0.81	0.87	0.81	0.84

TABLE VI
EXPERIMENT III-B: COMPARING CONCATENATION CLASSIFIERS ON FIREXPOSTS

Language	Model	Acc	Prec	Rec	F1
English	LinearSVM	0.78	0.72	0.77	0.74
	LR	0.78	0.72	0.76	0.74
	DT	0.77	0.71	0.76	0.73
	RF	0.78	0.69	0.77	0.73
Greek	LinearSVM	0.80	0.89	0.80	0.84
	LR	0.81	0.90	0.80	0.85
	DT	0.78	0.81	0.82	0.81
	RF	0.81	0.85	0.83	0.84

The notable performance of ShuffleNetV2-OnFire is attributed to its meticulously crafted architecture, as elucidated by [35] (Table IV), which renders it less computationally demanding without compromising its efficacy. Consequently, it surpasses its lightweight counterparts (NasNet-A-OnFire and MobileNet) and rivals Xception. Additionally, its high scores are attributed to its pre-training on both ImageNet and a Fire-related dataset before further fine-tuning it. Specifically, it has the highest values in accuracy and precision, same value in f1-score and slightly lower recall values with the Xception model. For these reasons, ShuffleNetV2-OnFire was selected as the model to be used for the fire detection on X post’s images.

E. Experiment III: Late Textual and Visual Analysis

Finally, in order to choose the best concatenation vector classifier, all aforementioned ML classifiers were trained on FireXPosts folds. The four best performing classifiers are presented in Table VI. In this series of experiments, all models exhibited similar performance, achieving comparable values in both languages. Apart from that, the slightly better results were from LinearSVM for the English language and LR on the Greek language subset. Table V) compares the two best performing classifiers for text and concepts extraction, the evaluation of Image-based fire detection on FireXPosts, and the three bi-modal fusion methods. The shallow neural tail was trained with the Adam optimizer over 100 epochs and a batch size of one, using binary cross-entropy loss. A custom learning rate scheduler was implemented, starting at 0.01 and reducing by a factor of ten twice: first after epoch 30 and again after epoch 80. In the case of the English language tail, all 4 activation functions (including the final classifier node) were sigmoid functions. In the case

of Greek, the three activation functions before the final sigmoid classifier found to be tanh functions.

Interestingly, the visual component of the shallow neural tail (up to N2) does not appear to positively influence the model’s outcome. This late-stage shallow network configuration seems incapable of effectively extracting significant information from visual predictions. This discrepancy between textual and visual information is also highlighted by the suboptimal performance of the Image-Based Fire Detection module on FireXPosts, as well as the outcomes of the majority voting fusion method.

V. CONCLUSION

Filtering fire posts on social media relevant to emergency responders is not a trivial task, due to the variability in public dataset annotation, modalities and end user needs. While visual modules can generally detect fires on images in an efficient manner, they do not seem to improve detection on the FireXPosts dataset. The proposed shallow neural tail appears to achieve similar scores compared to text modality models in English contexts. However, for Greek posts, the text modality appears superior to late fusion methods.

Future work should involve evaluating similar late fusion methods on the CrisisMMD dataset for fire detection. Efforts should also focus on leveraging models developed with DC2020 or CrisisMMD to enhance performance on the FireXPosts dataset. Additionally, exploring options to expand the annotation categories of FireXPosts, will be beneficial for end users or projects with requirements that are not restricted to emergency response.

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